

Selected historical documents regarding the IMIA Language and Meaning Working Group existence, naming and activities up to the latest renaming from ‘Medical Concept Representation’ WG to ‘Language and Meaning in Biomedicine’ WG

Date	WG name	Chair	Available historical facts, output	Source
1981	WORKING GROUP 7 – THE CODING AND CLASSIFICATION OF HEALTH DATA.	D. Shires	(WG mentioned the first time) Shires presented this proposal pointing out the needed collaboration with WHO.	http://www.ict-21.ch/com-ict/IMG/pdf/the-IFIP-silver-summary.pdf
1984 – 1985	IMIA WG6 – The Role of Informatics in the Classification and Coding of Health Data	RA Cote	Ottawa meeting: ROLE OF INFORMATICS IN HEALTH DATA CODING AND CLASSIFICATION SYSTEMS 1985; 410pp. Proceedings of the IMIA Working Conference (Dfl. 160.00) Ottawa, Ontario, Canada, September 1984 (R.A. Cote, D.J. Protti, J.R. Scherer, Eds.) North-Holland, Amsterdam	http://infohistory.rutgers.edu/imia-documents/1984/1984%20GA%20Minutes.pdf
1986	IMIA WG 6 - ROLE OF INFORMATICS IN HEALTH DATA CODING AND CLASSIFICATION SYSTEMS	RA Cote	Geneva meeting planned	http://infohistory.rutgers.edu/imia-documents/1987/1987%20GA%20Minutes.pdf
1989	IMIA WG 6 - The Coding and Classification of Health Data	RA Cote	WG6 achieved a successful working Conference in Geneva (WHO).	http://infohistory.rutgers.edu/imia-documents/1988/1988%20GA%20Minutes.pdf
1990	IMIA SIG proposal for replacing WG 6: Medical concepts structure for knowledge representation (not accepted)	RA. Cote	Proposal of SIG by Cote: A SIG on medical concepts structure for knowledge representation could replace WG6 (Nomenclatures and classifications) since its usefulness has ended after the last Conference in Geneva in 1988. Until the next GA, R. Cote was asked to study further this proposal in the former WG6 framework.	http://infohistory.rutgers.edu/imia-documents/1991/1991%20GA%20012%20WGs%20+%20SIGs.pdf
1994	WG-6 Coding and Classification of Health Data	JR. Scherrer	WG’s activity: Vevey meeting: Suggestion for Christopher Chute should succeed him as new WG-6 chairman	http://infohistory.rutgers.edu/imia-documents/1994/1994%20GA%20Minutes.pdf
1995	WG-6 Coding and Classification of Health Data	CG. Chute	There is a closing report by Jean-Raoul Scherrer. From the beginning of this year Christopher Chute has taken over the IMIA WG 6 Chairmanship.	http://infohistory.rutgers.edu/imia-documents/1995/1995%20GA%20008%20WGs+SIGs.pdf
1996	WG-6 Classification, Language, and Concept Representation	CG. Chute	working meeting planned of the committee during January 19-22, 1997, Jacksonville	http://infohistory.rutgers.edu/imia-documents/1996/1996%20GA%20105d%20WG6%20Concept%20representation.pdf
1997	WG-6 Classification, Language, and Concept Representation	CG. Chute	Jacksonville meeting document	http://infohistory.rutgers.edu/imia-documents/1997/1997%20GA%20001%20WG6%20Classification,%20Language,%20and%20Concept%20Representation%20CG%20Chute.pdf
1998	WG-6 Coding and Classification of Health Data	CG. Chute	A busy year for this WG. The group has been very active in the ISO Advisory Committee	http://infohistory.rutgers.edu/imia-documents/1998/GA98MIN.PDF
1999	WG 6 Medical Concept Representation	CG. Chute	Objective: To Provide a forum for state of the art dialogue and collaboration on natural language processing and concept representation in healthcare applications. IMIA WG6 is the international forum for issues related to informatics in the classification and coding of health data, and is charged with: 1) reviewing health data nomenclature and classification needs for the world community; 2) evaluating information processing technology in meeting these defined needs; and 3) recommending methods for future classification and nomenclature systems.	http://infohistory.rutgers.edu/imia-documents/1999/GA99-AGE.PDF
2000	WG 6 Medical Concept Representation	CG. Chute	Christopher Chute informed the meeting that the Phoenix meeting held at the end of 1999, as a conference was financially self-sustaining	http://infohistory.rutgers.edu/imia-documents/2000/2000%20GA%20Minutes.pdf

2001	WG 6 Medical Concept Representation	CG. Chute	A Medinfo panel proposal has been submitted by WG6, with joint sponsorship from the corresponding EFMI and AMIA working groups. A WG administrative session is planned for Medinfo, which will explore plans for the 2003 triennial conference.	http://infohistory.rutgers.edu/imia-documents/2001/2001%20GA%20012%20VP%20WGs%20+%20SIGs.pdf
2007 - 2011	WG Medical Concept Representation	O. Bodenreider	The LinkedIn group (http://www.linkedin.com/groups?home=&gid=3680642&trk=anet_ug_hm), administered by Laszlo Balkanyi, provides a platform for exchange of information (e.g., about conferences and publications of interest) and has 51 registered members to date	https://imia-medinfo.org/wp/wp-content/uploads/2012beijing/1210GA-beijing%20-vp-wgsig-reports.pdf
2012	WG Medical Concept Representation	O. Bodenreider	The IMIA WG6 was a sponsor of the International Conference on Biomedical Ontology (ICBO 2011), University at Buffalo, NY, USA, July 26-30, 2011 (http://icbo.buffalo.edu/). The proceedings are publicly available at http://ceurws.org/Vol-833/	https://imia-medinfo.org/wp/wp-content/uploads/2012beijing/1210GA-beijing%20-vp-wgsig-reports.pdf
2012	WG Medical Concept representation	S Schulz	(GA minutes)	https://imia-medinfo.org/wp/wp-content/uploads/GA-SaoPaulo-2015/WGSIG-VP-PART-III-V2.pdf
2014	WG Language and Meaning in Biomedicine	S Schulz	(GA minutes New Delhi) WG Name Change: Moved IMIA accept the request of Medical Concept Representation WG to change WG name and scope to Language and Meaning in Biomedicine	https://imia-medinfo.org/wp/sao-paulo-general-assembly/